

A Review On Fault Classification Methodologies In Transformer

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Abstract

This paper presents a survey on different fault classification methodologies in transformer, when the transformer becomes operational, it experiences a magnetizing inrush current with a magnitude that can range from six to eight times the rated current. This can cause the differential relay to trigger incorrectly and cutting off the transformer's supply lines without need. To avoid deceptively tripping the differential relay and make sure the transformer is operating properly, it's critical to differentiate between inrush current and internal fault current. The second harmonic restraint relay is used by traditional protection systems to distinguish between the internal fault current and the inrush current. The scale and complexity of power systems are growing along with the energy demand, making rapid, stable, and dependable protection systems necessary to preserve crucial components like transformers. Thus, current research focuses on creating unique algorithms for precise separation between internal fault current and inrush current. This review study, which is meant to help researchers new to this topic, examines numerous methods used to distinguish between internal fault current and inrush current in transformers.

Keywords: Transformer, magnetizing current, fault current, differential protection

1. Introduction

A transformer is an essential element of the power system that plays a role in the electromagnetic induction transmission of electrical energy from one circuit to another. To ensure its safety and proper operation, a protection system must be in place. Internal and external faults are the two types of problems that might occur in a transformer. External faults happen outside the transformer or at its terminals, whereas internal faults happen inside the transformer. Various kinds of protection systems are used, depending on the rating and state of operation of the transformer, to safeguard it against internal faults. For distribution transformers with small ratings, high-voltage fuses are utilized for transformers with values greater than 500 kVA, Buchholz relay protection is used.

In addition to the Buchholz relay, over-current protection with limited earth fault prevention is used for bigger distribution transformers. A differential relay compares the transformer's primary and secondary currents to protect power transformers using a differential protection technique. The relay sends a trip signal to both the primary and secondary circuit breakers if it detects a disparity.

Eliminating inappropriate relay trips brought on by the transformer's energizing magnetizing inrush current is one of the main challenges of differential protection. It can be challenging to distinguish between the internal fault current and this current because the former can occasionally be higher. A number of strategies have been developed for differentiating between inrush and internal fault currents, including harmonic restraint, voltage and flux restraint, the inductance-based method, the pattern recognition method, and artificial intelligence methods like neural networks and fuzzy logic.

While going through various research papers we found various points. Almost all the studies report scope for methods like many signal processing techniques and intelligence methods have been used to improve the fault and inrush detection. Variety types of architectures of artificial neural networks were used but those methods work on a particular transformer and its required some computation to the relay.

There are some variations of wavelet transforms, like boundary wavelet transforms [20], discrete wavelet transforms [19], wavelet packet transforms [18], and those WTs are used in differential protection, the performance of these methods is moderate. Still there are scope of these methods in practical applications, like- time delay to real-time analysis, and failure in overdamped transients. Wavelet analysis is a technique to analysis frequency. This technique is much better than conventional technique, because of its complex characteristics.

Power transformers are subject to internal faults and various transients when connected to the power system. These transients occur due to the equipment characteristics, such as magnetizing currents, effects from nearby connected equipment, such as sympathetic inrush. Thus, to ensure that the proposed methodology is able to identify different types of internal faults and distinguish them from the inrush conditions in power transformers and various transients. In order to determine the potential for new researchers, a comparative analysis of several inrush and internal fault current discrimination approaches is presented in this paper. These methods can be used to make sure that transformers are properly protected and prevent serious damage from internal defects.

2. Survey on fault classification methods

In the literature, there are several methods for differentiating between the internal fault current of a transformer and inrush current. In this study, a few of the most widely utilized strategies are reviewed.

2.1 Harmonic restraint method

The current-based method for transformer differential protection is described in [2]. In this paper the problem of transformer differential protection and discuss magnetizing inrush, over excitation, and CT saturation phenomena as possible causes of relay maloperation. Most transformer differential relays use the harmonics of the operating current to distinguish internal faults from Magnetizing inrush or over excitation conditions. The harmonics can be used to restrain or to block relay operation. Harmonic restraint and blocking methods ensure relay security for a very high percentage of inrush and over excitation cases. However, these methods fail for cases with very low harmonic content in the operating current. Common harmonic restraint or blocking increases differential relay security, but could delay relay operation for internal faults combined with inrush currents in the non-faulted phases So Wave shape recognition techniques represent another alternative for discriminating internal faults from inrush conditions.

In this method interturn fault identification system and the detection of winding displacement is done by using the search coil. The algorithm precisely detects the location of the fault. Voltage analysis of search coil is done to discriminate the interturn fault and radial winding displacement. Impedance analyzer plots are used to verify the results experimentally. The proposed method works accurately irrespective of the operating condition and configuration of transformer [57].

The behavior of the differential currents' second harmonic components under inrush and fault conditions served as the basis for the creation of an algorithm. The temporal variation of the second harmonic of differential current was used to define the criteria function, and the sign of the criterion function was assessed for the three phases. The method distinguishes between internal faults and inrush current within half a cycle of the event, without using thresholding [63].

By summing all the magnitudes of all 2nd harmonics from three phases a single harmonic signal has been produced. The resultant content is accorded to determine the ratio of 2nd harmonic for every phase. If there is even a very weak 2nd harmonic in any phase, the shared harmonic calculated from will be high, and 2nd harmonic ratio will enhance larger enough to restrain the differential protection method from maloperation. If an internal fault is detected in a phase at the time of energization. If the value of the fundamental current surges very high the consequence is a low harmonic ratio. Therefore, there is less chance to arise a difficulty from a faulted phase. So, the tripping of a three-phase transformer will occur during an internal fault. By harmonic summing technique security against maloperation has improved [3]

Per-Condition Analysis is the most naive and most classical method to restraint harmonics. In every phase the restraint algorithm is parallel and self-governing. [3] In the Per – Condition Analysis, this criterion uses to each phase independently. In each phase, the remaining flux is different. So, in each phase, the magnitude of 2nd harmonic will be varied. This method operates on the threshold value. Thus, if the 2nd harmonic content is weak in a phase while energizing, the differential protection may trip. That's why this method is reliable but not very defended. [2]

Since various residual flux applies to each phase Energization of each phase has been made at a different angle, every phase will have a distinct level of harmonics. When the amount of the ratio of second harmonic for a specific phase is more numerous than a preset level, the percent differential process will be inhibited in that phase. There is an opportunity of having a ratio of weak second harmonic for each phase at the period of transformer energization.

Undesirable may occur in the three-phase transformer, If there is a small ratio of the second harmonic in a phase during differential operation [3]

This method has an intermediary with Per-Phase Method, the single difference is that the signal which is restraint from a phase will restrain differential operation for all another phase. Differential protection will trip at above the preset value of second harmonic for other phases also. In the case of a symmetrical fault, this method works well. But if there is a single unsymmetrical fault, the differential protection will trip [2]. This method restricts the occurrence of false tripping by improving safety because this method allows the phase with a ratio of weak harmonic to be cross-blocked by a phase with a higher ratio. This cross-blocking method is well reliable but not so trustworthy, in [3] two methods similar to a cross-blocking method in this differential operation needs at least 2 phases to identify the satisfactory level of harmonics. But this approach also has the same primary drawback of the simple cross-blocking technique. [3]

In this technique [3], harmonic ratio determines the average of the 2nd harmonic ratio of three phases, the safety of the differential protection has been raised by this percentage average blocking method. So, this technique is more secure, If there is a large harmonic ratio in the remaining phases, it is highly possible that the differential operation will be restrained owing to a true single-phase fault during energization. There appears an interest correlating to the dependability in the differential protection.

The protection system may not be able to discriminate between inrush and fault current if a fault develops during transformer energization. Since the second harmonic component predominates in inrush currents, a new method exploits second harmonic restraint to discriminate between the fundamental and second harmonic components of inrush and fault currents [64].

In comparison to differential relays implementing only one differential element, those using both the blocking differential element and the second harmonic restraint in tandem operate more quickly. This is because parallel processing speeds things up. In comparison to the traditional differential element, the negative-sequence differential element offers increased sensitivity for imbalanced faults. Turn-to-turn defects can be detected because to this increased sensitivity [65].

The second harmonic restraint technique is frequently used to assure dependable operation of relays during inrush conditions. Lower second harmonic components during magnetizing inrush currents are the result of enhanced magnetic characteristics of transformer cores brought about by advancements in technology. However, due to CT saturation and the impact of distributed capacitance in EHV lines, the second harmonic components get amplified during short-circuit currents. Selecting a suitable harmonic restraint ratio is made difficult by this. A quick flux restraint method that employs sampled voltage and current measurements to determine the inrush current has been presented as a solution to this problem. The saturation status of the transformer is determined by this method by measuring the rate at which the magnetic flux in the transformer core changes. A counter group monitors the saturation status, and the relay generates a trip instruction to isolate the transformer based on the counter threshold [66].

2.2 Signal Processing Techniques

A novel digital directional transformer protection technique based on wavelet packet described in [36]. In this paper, suggested directional signal combined from the voltage and current measurements has distinguishing characteristics enable it to be identified. The wavelet packet transform (WPT) is an extension of the FWT that allows for finer characterization of signal content for both time and frequency together. The wavelet packets are a more sensitive and computationally more flexible way to do signal discrimination than FFT- or standard FWT-based methods. A wavelet-based method has been presented in [36]. The drawback of this method is that it requires the measurement of voltage in addition to current that increases the cost of hardware implementation.

New algorithms based on the wavelet packet transform (WPT) to diagnose magnetizing inrush, internal fault and normal (through-fault) currents in three-phase power transformers described in [38]. In this paper, the data was collected using a harmonic restraint approach. The data collection procedure and the condition in which both inrush current and internal fault not present simultaneously. This algorithm has not been considered the condition in which both inrush current and internal fault present simultaneously

A new wavelet-based method to identify inrush currents and to distinguish it from power system faults described in [39]. Fast emerging field of WT, the property of multi resolution in time and frequency provided by wavelets is described, which allows accurate time location of transient components while simultaneously retaining information about the fundamental frequency and its low harmonics. This paper demonstrates that the algorithm successfully

differentiates between magnetizing inrush and fault conditions in less than half power frequency cycle. The ability of the WT to focus on short time intervals for high-frequency components and long intervals for low-frequency components improves the analysis of signals with localized impulses and oscillations. For this reason, wavelet decomposition is ideal for studying transient signals and obtaining a much better current characterization and a more reliable discrimination.

The WT approach has attracted number of applications especially in the field of power system. Recent progress in the application of WT technology to the power system in the area of power transformer protection made it overcome some of the limitations in conventional protection system problem. A Wavelet-Based Algorithm for Discrimination of Internal Faults from Magnetizing Inrush Currents in Transformers is described in [40]. This improved strategy uses a method which focused on a new algorithm based on differential protection of transformer by considering different behavior of differential current under fault and inrush current condition. This algorithm gives higher accuracy for considering different behavior of the differential current under faults and inrush current condition. As the internal fault and inrush current are extracted, then by quantifying the extracted features a criterion function is define in terms of difference of amplitude of wavelet coefficients over a specific frequency band due to fault and inrush current. A new algorithm is very quick and accurate.

Adaptative differential protection of three phase power transformers based on transient signal analysis is described in [44]. In this paper, an adaptive method using the spectral energy analysis extracted from the differential currents by DWT. The method developed proved to be robust in the internal fault conditions discrimination and other simulated transients, but it needs to set an adaptive threshold, and it has not been tested in internal faults conditions, which are difficult to identify, such as the inter-turn fault in power transformers.

A reliable setting-free technique for power transformer protection based on wavelet transform is described in [46], this paper presents a new methodology based on the analysis and monitoring of the discrete wavelet transform (DWT) detail coefficients for internal fault conditions identification and discrimination in power transformers. The method is based on the analysis and monitoring of signals variation through DWT decomposition levels.

A unique technique based on correlation coefficient analysis is used to distinguish between inrush and internal faults in a transformer. The approach is based on changes in current waveforms that occur during faults. In one technique, auto-correlation is combined with cross correlation for improved fault discrimination and faster fault detection. This strategy efficiently solves the CT saturation problem. The algorithm is evaluated practically with LabVIEW and MATLAB, and the results show that it can detect and properly identify inrush and internal transformer problems [16]

Wavelet analysis is a technique to analysis frequency, this technique is much better than the traditional technique, because of its multiple characteristics. There are three types of wavelet transform-Discrete wavelet transform, continuous wavelet transform and wavelet transform.so as to decompose the signal at various frequencies at a specific time, this method of selecting the mother wavelet is used. In order to provide relevant information regarding the distinction of inrush current from internal fault current of a power transformer the Daubechies (db4) mother wavelet with two levels of resolution provides the most optimal result. To select the optimal mother wavelet and no. resolution level, the least description length criterion has been used in [1][13][21].

2.3 Techniques pertaining to Signal Processing and Soft Computing

A new relaying algorithm to enhance the fault detection sensitivities of conventional techniques by using a fuzzy logic approach described in [34]. The proposed fuzzy-based relaying algorithm consists of flux-differential current derivative curve, harmonic restraint, and percentage differential characteristic curve. Differential current harmonics are used as inputs to a trained fuzzy logic in [34].

Fuzzy logic-based relaying for power transformer protection described in [35]. To enhance the fault detection sensitivity of traditional percentage differential current relaying algorithm, fuzzy logic approaches are used to obtain clear fault discrimination between magnetizing inrush and internal faults. The problem associated with these methods is the need to design neural networks or fuzzy laws, which require a huge number of training patterns produced by simulations of various cases [35].

Using a fuzzy logic-based method to take care off of the possible imperfect operation of the differential relay during magnetizing inrush current, the inrush current and the fault current can be discriminated in this system, the percentage of the content of second harmonic is more significant than the magnitude. While the fault occurs, second harmonic content and complete harmonic distortion go lower than 5%. Therefore, the threshold value has to consider for 3 factors. Those factors are total harmonic distortion, second harmonic ratio, and second harmonic magnitude. The deciding factor of fault in a phase does not affect the deciding factors of other phases. Therefore, the probability of differential protection having unrequired operation gets decreases. These characteristics make this method more secure, more reliable and advanced. [2][13][14].

A neural network-based algorithm for the protection of a single-phase power transformer is described in [33]. The neural network input is a four-dimensional vector obtained by a fast-frequency analysis of the differential current. Primary and secondary currents are measured with current transformers the saturation of which is taken into account. A set of training cases is generated with the help of the electromagnetic transients program. A differential current harmonic is used as inputs to a trained neural network. The problem associated with these methods is the approach need to retraining for use in other power transformer systems if the transformer, for example, is changed in capacity and voltage ratings as well as iron-core constructions and winding connections.

Also, some Methods using ANN based method [26], mathematical morphology and ANN based method [27], GSA trained ANN method [28], Hilbert transform ANN approached method [29], are used to identify the inrush current and faults.

A method based on the artificial intelligence (AI) techniques described in [37]. In this paper, the wavelet transformer feature extractor are fed into a well-trained neural network to specify the faults. This paper shows that the Wavelet Transform and artificial neural network suitable for discriminate power transformer inrush current and application it in differential protection. The combination of feature extraction based on WT and classification method based on neural networks. Algorithm required a huge number of training patterns. Wavelet Transform representation guarantees an observable feature pattern of the signals. It also demonstrates the ability of the combined network for fault diagnosis. The obtained results show that the proposed ANN-based inrush detector represents a proper action and makes the diagnostic inrush currents. In [37] an algorithm has been recommended using a combination of the WT and neural network. In this method a WT has been used as a preprocessor and the output of the wavelet is the input of the artificial neural network. The required algorithm training and other above-mentioned problems are the drawbacks of the algorithm.

Discrimination between internal faults and other disturbances in the transformer using the support vector machine-based protection system is explained in [45]. If fault type is not identified quickly, it might enhance a major serious fault which may result in the appearance of an arc inside the transformer tank

Different artificial intelligence (AI)-based techniques have been used in the detection and diagnosis of rotating electrical machine faults [47]. Recently, some of these techniques have been applied for transformers. These techniques are based on the use of artificial neural networks (ANN), fuzzy logic (FL), support vector machines (SVM) [48, 49], and probabilistic neural networks [50, 51] among other variants [52, 53]. These techniques try to improve the sensibility and versatility of external disturbances of the differential protection relays. Although in many situations, they have been useful, the disadvantages of these methods lie in the fact that they require precise training patterns and sets of expert rules for each case.

In [54] presents an algorithm based on a combination of the wavelet discrete transform with a model obtained with neural networks for the detection and classification of internal faults in a three-phase two-winding transformer [54]. In this way, in [55], an improvement to the previous algorithm is proposed, which allows reducing the training time of the neural network. This alternative is based on the use of a back-propagation network for faults location between turns and offers better response times, simplicity, and accuracy in different fault conditions.

An algorithm based on ANN is presented for fault identification in the transformer in [56], in this method, the first, second, and fifth harmonic components of the positive sequence differential current are the inputs. Although this method responds accurately to different transient situations, it distinguishes internal faults from external, between other convenient aspects, the method cannot be generalized to be applied to different power transformers.

2.4 Microprocessor Based Technique

A Microcontroller based protection system is used for the protection of power transformer. This system consists of hardware circuitry used to discriminate between inrush current and internal fault current. This protection system works reliably and it does not generate the trip signal in case of normal operation, inrush phenomenon and external fault conditions. The operating time of this scheme is very less [67].

2.5 FPGA Technique

A new method is proposed for discrimination of inrush current and internal fault current on the basis of nature of current waveform, magnitude and duration. In this algorithm the magnitude and duration of both inrush current and internal fault current are compared with the help of FPGA. After comparison the FPGA makes the decision and gives the output to provide the trip signal in case of internal fault and to pass the inrush current [68].

2.6 Morphology Technique

The mathematical morphology-based approach towards developing an inrush blocking scheme for transformer differential protection. Inrush identification is carried by considering the morphological gradient of the differential current waveform. Depending on the characteristics of the derived waveforms and their correlation, the inrush currents are distinguished from the fault currents. Validation of the performance of the proposed algorithm is done in two stages: MATLAB simulation and comparative analysis with a standard relay [30].

There are various methodologies, like morphological gradient (MG) [15], signal decomposition [17], which are utilized in these algorithms. This technique performs well in case of various scenarios such as recovery inrush, sympathetic inrush or CT saturation.

In [43] Waveform Analysis of Differential Current Signal to Identify Magnetizing Inrush in Power Transformer is defined. First, the differential current signal in power transformer is stored and its essential features during magnetizing inrush conditions are presented. Secondly, an adaptive generalized morphological filter is designed to overcome the noise in differential current signal. At last, the complexity of signal waveform is evaluated by applying the grille fractal. As the waveform complexity is much higher in magnetizing inrush than in fault condition, the proposed method can assuredly and accurately identify transformer inrush from faults.

3. Conclusion

Power transformers are critical for the stable and reliable operation of power systems, and they must be protected. Malfunctions in differential protection systems are frequently caused by magnetizing inrush currents, making it critical to promptly and reliably distinguish between inrush and internal fault current. In this paper, an analytical and extensive review of various techniques used for discrimination between inrush current & internal fault current of transformer with their advantages & limitations is presented. This study examines various strategies for distinguishing between these currents while taking into account the transformer's rating, application, and detection time. Signal processing and soft computing methods are chosen for the discrimination of inrush current & internal fault current of transformer. Existing methods are for identifying inrush and internal fault currents in transformers require improvement in accuracy, computational time, and complexity.

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